

ADAPTED TO THE ECOLOGY OF UZBEKISTAN PLANTS AND ANIMALS

Xolmaxmadova Elzoda Uktam qizi

Faculty of Pedagogy, Shahrissabz State Pedagogical Institute Biology student

Toshniyozov Hasan Berdiyov o'g'li

A student of the Termiz branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy

Abstract: This article provides detailed information about ephemerals, ephemeroids, plants adapted to the desert (plain), gypsum desert, saline soils, and animal species found in shallow waters, forests, rivers, and mountain plains.

Key words: Adaptation, ephemeral plants, individual, vertebrates and invertebrates, correlation, cnidarians, ctenophores, sponges.

Plant life in the desert (plain) is mainly associated with sand and gypsum soils and sorghum. The sandy desert includes Kyzylqum, the dry bed of Kashkadarya (Sandiqlikum), Kattakum in the lower part of Surkhandarya, and sandy massifs in the Khorezm basin. Most dunes are fortified with vegetation. White saxophone, juzgun (candy), cherkez from trees or large bushes in sand dunes; from the bushes grow such plants as white paint, rabbit bone, red rose, cherry tree. Juzgun roots grow up to 20 m to the side and retain sand to a certain extent. Selenium from perennial grasses is of particular importance in strengthening sands. It prevents the movement of sand with its scattered roots and above-ground parts (stems) and creates conditions for the growth of other plants (juzgun, saxovul, etc.) by trapping its seeds. It is also propagated through the rhizome of a perennial ephemeral plant adapted to growing in sand. It grows quickly, blooms and bears fruit in the short spring months.

Gypsum desert includes certain areas (massives) located in Ustyurt, southwestern and northwestern Kyzylqum. Gypsum desert flora is not very rich in species. In the formation of the formation (community) of plants, mainly the species belonging to the symbionts take part. In particular, among the semi-evergreen shrubs, you can find a lot of ephemerals, such as burgun, voyalich, and one-year shuras (fisheye), white gorse belonging to the wormwood family.

Depending on the amount of salts in saline soils, the vegetation varies. Wet, clayey and soft saline soils are very unfavorable for plant development. But, despite this, in some places there are plants such as sarizazan, qizilshora, karabaraq, shohilak,

aqbash, buzoqbash, donashor, shura, ajrig. In general, the number of species growing in such conditions is more than 100. Among the common plants in shorhoks are saxovul (both types) and many representatives of the family of shoroks (fisheye, hare, black shora). They are adapted to growing in the harsh (hot and dry) conditions of the desert in different ways, that is, some of them have seret leaves and stems, while others have thorny leaves or no leaves at all.

Areas that were once under shallow water—barrens—have very few plants. Only in some cases can you see some ephemerals and plants such as grain saltpeter emerging from the barren cracks. There are such balds in Kyzylkum deserts.

Forests are located along the banks of rivers (especially Amudarya and Syrdarya) in different widths and lengths. In forests, mainly trees, shrubs and perennial grasses are common. From the trees, there are several representatives of turongil (from the poplar family), kaptarchia, and willow family; pluck from the bushes; from perennial grasses, sweet cranberries, some types of bilberry, reeds, reeds, and famasia grow.

The foothills are mainly covered with annual and perennial grasses. There are no trees here. Some bushes are found around streams where spring rainwater flows. In the foothills, ephemeral and ephemeroid plants are widespread and form a specific group and association (population).

Annual plants (ephemerals) develop in the fall when the weather is warm and sunny, and continue to grow in winter depending on the weather. Development is more rapid in the southern regions. As early as March-April, ephemerals bloom in a relatively short period of time, and they have time to finish fruiting. Ephemerooids (perennial grasses) like ephemerals grow in autumn, winter and spring according to the weather. But bulbous and rhizome ephemerooids, life processes continue underground in autumn and winter. For example, tulip buds form under the soil. The most common ephemerooids are a number of species belonging to the family "Konkirbosh" and "Ilak". In addition to these, you can also find some types of wax, wormwood, and carpet.

The concept of animals includes the sum of all multicellular, eukaryotic organisms of the Animal Kingdom living on our planet. The animal world includes both wild individuals and domesticated ones. Man is also in the natural taxonomy of fauna. Animals can be divided into Vertebrates have a spine or vertebral column and their number is less than 3% of all described species of the fauna. These include: fish, amphibians, reptiles, birds and mammals. The rest of the animals are invertebrates, which are characterized by the absence of a backbone. These include: crustaceans

(mussels, oysters, octopus, squid, snails); arthropods (centipedes, insects, spiders, scorpions, crabs, lobsters, crabs); annelids (earthworms, leeches), nematodes, flatworms (tapeworms), cnidarians (jellyfish, sea anemones, corals), ctenophores and sponges. The study of animals is called science.

Adaptation (lat. adaptatio - adaptation) - 1) adaptation of the organism to different living conditions; 2) a change in the level of sensitivity of the sense organs as a result of adaptation to the stimuli affecting them (for example, adaptation of the eye to light or darkness). As the strength of the stimulus changes, so does the sensitivity. Sensitivity increases when stimuli are weak, and decreases when they are strong. The process of adaptation is strongly formed in animals.

Types of adaptation A change in the entire form of an organism's existence is a functional adaptation. An example of correlative adaptation or co-adaptation is when changing conditions cause living organisms to adapt to each other. Adaptation can be passive, if the subject's functions or structure occur without his participation, or it can be active, when he consciously changes his habits in accordance with the environment (examples of people adapting to natural conditions or society). There are cases when the subject adapts the environment to his needs - this is objective adaptation. Biologists distinguish types of adaptation according to three criteria: Morphological. Physiological. behavioral or psychological. Examples of pure adaptation of animals or plants are rare, most cases of adaptation to new conditions occur in mixed forms. Adaptation means to adapt or get used to. It is a process of gradual rebirth of physiological, morphological or psychological functions of an organism in a changed environment. Both individuals and entire populations undergo changes. A vivid example of direct and indirect adaptation is the survival of flora and fauna in the zone of increased radiation around the Chernobyl nuclear power plant. Direct adaptation is characteristic of people who managed to survive, adapted and began to reproduce, some died without being able to pass the test (indirect adaptation).

Since the conditions of existence on earth are constantly changing, the processes of evolution and adaptation in living nature are also a continuous process.

A recent example of adaptation is the habitat change of a colony of green Mexican parrots. Recently, they changed their usual habitat and settled in the mouth of the Masaya volcano, in an environment that is constantly saturated with high concentration of sulfate gas. Scientists have not yet commented on this phenomenon.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Bogdanov S.P. O`zbekiston hayvonlari. -T:. O`qituvchi, 1983. –B.23-56
2. Dubovskiy G.K.,Ummatov A.M. Zoologiyadan o`quv qo`llanma.- T:. O`qituvchi, 1991. – B.56-71.
3. Kuznetsov B.A.,Chernov A.Z., Katanova L.N. Kurs zoologii. -M., «Agropromizdat», 1989.
4. Muxammadiyev A.M. Umurtqasiz hayvonlar zoologiyasi. -T:. O`qituvchi, 1976. 86b.